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FURAN-BASED CHALCONES DERIVATIVES: SYNTHESIS, ANTIOXIDANT EVALUATION, DFT CALCULATIONS AND ADME PREDICTIONS

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Supplementary Material

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Figure S1. ^1H , ^{13}C , HMBC and HSQC NMR spectrum (400 MHz, CDCl_3) of chalcone 3-(2-Furano)-1-phenyl-prop-2-en-1-one (Compound_1).

^1H -NMR

^{13}C -NMR

HMBC (^1H - ^{13}C)

Figure S2. ^1H , ^{13}C , HMBC and HSQC NMR spectrum (400 MHz, CDCl_3) of chalcone 3-(2-furan)-1-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-2-propen-1-one (Compound_2).

^1H -NMR

^{13}C -NMR

HMBC (^1H - ^{13}C)

Figure S3. ^1H , ^{13}C , HMBC and HSQC NMR spectrum (400 MHz, CDCl_3) of chalcone 3-(2-furan)-1-(2-nitrophenyl)-2-propen-1-one (Compound_3).

^1H -NMR

^{13}C -NMR

HMBC (^1H - ^{13}C)

Figure S4. ^1H , ^{13}C , HMBC and HSQC NMR spectrum (400 MHz, CDCl_3) of chalcone 3-(2-furan)-1-(2-bromophenyl)-2-propen-1-one (Compound_4).

^1H -NMR

^{13}C -NMR

HMBC (^1H - ^{13}C)

Figure S5. ^1H , ^{13}C , HMBC and HSQC NMR spectrum (400 MHz, CDCl_3) of chalcone 3-(2-furan)-1-(2-hydroxy-5-nitrophenyl)-2-propen-1-one (Compound_5).

^1H -NMR

^{13}C -NMR

HMBC (^1H - ^{13}C)

Supplement S6. Regression curves, fitted equations, and raw concentration–response data.

Quercetin

Compound_1

Compound_2

Compound_3

Compound_4

Compound_5

Supplement S7. Inputs DFT**Neutral Molecule**

```
! B3LYP def2-TZVP TightSCF Opt Freq
```

```
%maxcore 2000
```

```
* xyz 0 1
```

```
*
```

Radical Molecule

```
! B3LYP def2-TZVP TightSCF Opt Freq
```

```
%maxcore 2000
```

```
%pal nprocs 4 end
```

```
* xyz 0 2
```

```
*
```

Supplement S8. Optimized coordinates DFT

Compound_1

----- CARTESIAN COORDINATES (ANGSTROEM) -----			
C	-0.801101	1.118097	-0.264289
C	-1.378905	-0.142896	-0.171457
C	-0.583682	-1.258727	0.061043
C	0.795492	-1.111401	0.190517
C	1.372543	0.144302	0.086068
C	0.582256	1.277668	-0.137101
C	1.275544	2.603938	-0.251537
O	2.491552	2.647995	-0.374364
C	0.465430	3.839029	-0.197029
C	1.048427	5.041406	-0.352660
C	0.398033	6.311742	-0.307985
C	0.882641	7.586617	-0.450464
C	-0.223017	8.468925	-0.310002
C	-1.307128	7.678126	-0.091957
O	-0.954645	6.370314	-0.086897
H	-1.438287	1.970152	-0.456651
H	-2.450640	-0.252729	-0.280912
H	-1.035189	-2.240129	0.139221
H	1.418447	-1.978778	0.370776
H	2.442596	0.276245	0.173622
H	-0.596849	3.775433	-0.011686
H	2.118678	5.067596	-0.529028
H	1.911543	7.849006	-0.633618
H	-0.216594	9.544554	-0.363236
H	-2.350255	7.887635	0.070717

Compound_2

----- CARTESIAN COORDINATES (ANGSTROEM) -----			
O	0.995442	0.081425	0.126708
C	2.326927	0.069172	0.032731
C	3.090749	1.264886	-0.071344
C	4.490416	1.145987	-0.166227
C	5.117732	-0.082678	-0.159682
C	4.347312	-1.245634	-0.056162
C	2.972510	-1.173711	0.038729
C	2.390704	2.561777	-0.075309
O	1.149366	2.601556	0.011172
C	3.149914	3.816380	-0.181002
C	2.510434	5.001338	-0.186165
C	3.117414	6.288740	-0.283361
C	2.576505	7.549256	-0.298688
C	3.658384	8.463107	-0.414073
C	4.785770	7.704260	-0.461097
O	4.482080	6.386854	-0.383524
H	0.725080	1.040052	0.105703
H	5.098507	2.035203	-0.246817
H	6.195228	-0.144213	-0.234007
H	4.831679	-2.214679	-0.050140
H	2.362013	-2.063549	0.119240
H	4.225873	3.789305	-0.255273
H	1.428528	4.998773	-0.110130
H	1.526266	7.781424	-0.234393
H	3.609555	9.538102	-0.456427
H	5.831693	7.944068	-0.545070

Compound_3

Compound_4

----- CARTESIAN COORDINATES (ANGSTROEM) -----			
O	2.555753	1.715452	-1.017454
N	3.380620	0.979531	-0.497815
O	4.189420	0.297192	-1.107977
C	3.420852	0.924498	0.976664
C	2.959605	2.042180	1.660373
C	3.052941	2.078562	3.043147
C	3.609182	1.000987	3.724111
C	4.060791	-0.110084	3.024479
C	3.968096	-0.180219	1.633562
C	4.441100	-1.471252	0.994563
O	5.542943	-1.895410	1.291147
C	3.482804	-2.213423	0.161910
C	3.801081	-3.425027	-0.329446
C	2.966851	-4.259893	-1.130267
C	3.182401	-5.494663	-1.687623
C	1.998111	-5.843941	-2.390391
C	1.139520	-4.803614	-2.216464
O	1.704575	-3.835798	-1.457564
H	2.553031	2.870154	1.098345
H	2.704788	2.949415	3.582861
H	3.693676	1.025299	4.803184
H	4.495257	-0.950046	3.550043
H	2.512482	-1.775595	-0.032741
H	4.786492	-3.820407	-0.106881
H	4.087190	-6.073198	-1.599688
H	1.807107	-6.743503	-2.950792
H	0.136351	-4.612335	-2.556416

----- CARTESIAN COORDINATES (ANGSTROEM) -----			
C	-0.709441	1.069447	-0.703330
C	-1.352633	-0.147148	-0.528654
C	-0.689596	-1.185141	0.113933
C	0.609079	-1.002172	0.572009
C	1.253487	0.212802	0.370632
C	0.606988	1.272537	-0.273816
C	1.268907	2.589363	-0.589569
O	2.382365	2.624481	-1.080515
C	0.489922	3.809195	-0.294401
C	0.994361	5.024428	-0.578291
C	0.373010	6.283323	-0.324656
C	0.790478	7.567797	-0.564384
C	-0.240043	8.431114	-0.104193
C	-1.216127	7.620418	0.385116
O	-0.866697	6.318375	0.261483
H	-1.224217	1.878696	-1.206545
H	-2.364568	-0.281739	-0.888393
H	-1.179708	-2.138436	0.266867
H	1.125210	-1.800041	1.087663
Br	3.022673	0.380615	1.074671
H	-0.475644	3.708545	0.182899
H	1.973572	5.069400	-1.044125
H	1.727358	7.848326	-1.016732
H	-0.256621	9.507580	-0.130925
H	-2.175243	7.812326	0.834336

Compound_5

----- CARTESIAN COORDINATES (ANGSTROEM) -----			
O	1.453220	0.082816	-0.403090
N	2.406567	-0.163714	0.325435
O	2.841166	-1.287551	0.536153
C	3.072042	0.958322	0.989131
C	2.605586	2.239316	0.772354
C	3.216582	3.334048	1.388921
C	4.330984	3.086703	2.243756
C	4.784527	1.772287	2.446694
C	4.163867	0.713956	1.826940
C	2.758277	4.728340	1.191413
O	3.354795	5.653288	1.771565
C	1.616706	5.014820	0.322947
C	1.202615	6.284966	0.135445
C	0.110286	6.702121	-0.681026
C	-0.809584	6.064886	-1.478532
C	-1.645414	7.067612	-2.028618
C	-1.187601	8.253137	-1.536129
O	-0.130981	8.055495	-0.722550
H	1.760031	2.359551	0.114870
O	4.968583	4.066998	2.866976
H	5.631982	1.621946	3.101664
H	4.502376	-0.301204	1.974000
H	1.107072	4.199207	-0.167581
H	1.740985	7.076380	0.646516
H	-0.875709	5.003034	-1.648086
H	-2.476163	6.932093	-2.700431
H	-1.499878	9.274452	-1.670228
H	4.506472	4.915079	2.599901